

On a New Method of Calculation of Vibration Frequencies of Atoms.

BY BINAYENDRA NATH SEN.

The frequency of vibration of atoms of elements has been the subject of investigation of several authors (Einstien, *Ann. Physik*, 1911, *iv*, 34, 170; Lindemann, *Physikal. Z.*, 1910, 11, 609; *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1911, 17, 822; *Ber. Phys. Ges.*, 1911, 13, 1107; Wagstaff, *Phil. Mag.*, 1924, *vi*, 47, 84). Each author has given his own formula for computing the value of atomic frequencies, which although of great theoretical interest and of practical importance, does not always give values in close agreement with the experimental ones. It was, therefore, thought by the present author that one or more of the factors on which the atomic frequency depends has been lost sight of and it is the object of the present paper to discuss such factors and propose a formula for the determination of atomic frequencies of elements which would give results in close agreement with the experimental ones.

In the present formula certain assumptions have been made with respect to the constraint on the atom. The atomic spheres which are capable of vibration about their mean positions in an environment full of energy may be considered to be under a certain state of tension determined by the parachor of the element and the electrical field in the neighbourhood. The constraint may be assumed to be directly proportional to $\frac{P-V}{V}$ where P is the parachor and V , the atomic volume of the element, as also to Ze^2/r^3 where Z is the valency, e the elementary charge and r , the atomic radius.

Supposing the substance contains a system of atomic vibrators of frequency ν , then according to the simple theory of harmonic motion,

$$\nu = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{p}{m}} \quad (1)$$

where ' m ' is the atomic mass and ' p ' the constraint on the atom.

Assuming the constraint on the atom to be proportional to the factors already indicated, the equation (1) changes to

$$\nu = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k \cdot \frac{P-V}{V} \cdot \frac{Ze^2}{r^3}}{m}}$$

We can finally have,

$$\nu = \sqrt{k} \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{P-V}{V} \cdot \frac{Ze^2}{r^3} \cdot \frac{N}{M}}$$

where $k = 0.415 \times 10^{12}$, $N = 6.06 \times 10^{23}$ (Avogadro's number) and $M =$ the atomic weight of the element.

The physical and mathematical significance of the relation

$$p = k \cdot \frac{P-V}{V} \cdot \frac{Ze^2}{r^3}$$

will form the subject of another communication.

The values for parachors of elements have been taken from Sugden's "Parachor and Valency," p. 181.

As regards the atomic radii of the different elements, Bragg's values (Bragg, *Phil. Mag.*, 1920, *vi*, 40, 169) have been throughout adopted in the calculations. In the absence of Bragg's value for the atomic diameter of mercury, Perrin's value (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1909, *viii*, 18, 5) has been taken as it has been confirmed by later work (cf. Henry, *Compt. rend.*, 1912, 154, 880); Saha's value, as it would appear from his own statement (*Nature*, 1921, 170, 682), is too small.

The values for the atomic volumes have been adopted from the tables used by Lewis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 29, 1165, 1516) and Wagstaff (*Phil. Mag.*, 1924, *vi*, 47, 84).

The question of selection of valencies appears to present some difficulty in the case of elements with variable valencies. In these cases such valency is adopted as is exhibited in the direct formation of chlorides or bromides by the action of halogens or in the indirect formation of the stablest halides.

Mercury has thus been assumed to be divalent because the free metal directly unites with chlorine to form the dichloride (Cowper, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1883, 43, 153; Balard, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1826, *ii*, 32, 337). Slight traces of mercurous chloride are, however, formed

owing to the reducing action of the metal but the compound is unstable and is dissociated in the vaporous state (Harris and Meyer, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 1842).

Lead has been assumed to be divalent in as much as lead chloride is only formed by the direct action of chlorine on the metal (Weber, *Pogg. Ann.*, 1861 112, 659; Fischer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1879, 35, 282).

Copper when heated in chlorine forms only the dichloride and is hence assumed to be divalent. Any trace of cuprous chloride formed, however, passes into the dichloride (Mellor, "Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. III. p. 168).

Arsenic forms only the trichloride when the free element burns in chlorine gas (Dumas, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1828, ii, 38, 337; Rose, *Pogg. Ann.*, 1841, 52, 62; Capitine, *J. Pharm. Chem.*, 1839, iii, 25, 524). Also, the pentachloride is dissociated at an elevated temperature into arsenic trichloride and chlorine. These have led us to assume arsenic to be a trivalent element.

Nickel and chromium have been assumed to be di- and trivalent elements respectively as they exhibit these valencies in their stable chlorides.

In the case of other elements dealt with in this paper their usual valencies have been adopted.

In the following tables the observed values of frequencies are those calculated by Nernst and Lindemann's atomic heat formula (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1911, 17, 822), which represents experimental values with great exactitude.

TABLE I.

Element.	Para-chor.	Atomic vol.	Atomic radius.	Val-ency.	Atomic wt.	ν cal.	ν obs.
Mercury	69.0	14.8	1.73	2	200.60	2.1×10^{12}	2.2×10^{12}
Lead	76.2	18.2	1.90	2	207.20	1.64	1.9
Iodine	91.0	25.7	1.40	1	126.92	2.1	2.0
Copper	46.0	7.10	1.37	2	63.57	6.35	6.6
Aluminium	38.6	10.1	1.35	3	27.10	8.7	8.3
Zinc	50.7	9.5	1.325	2	65.37	5.8	4.8×10^{13}

TABLE II.

Elements.	Para-chor.	Atomic vol.	Atomic radius.	Val-ency.	Atomic wt.	ν cal.	ν obs.
Bromine	68·0	25·1	1·19	1	79·92	$2·76 \times 10^{12}$...
Silicon	25·0	11·4	1·175	4	28·30	9·96	...
Chlorine	54·3	25·0	1·05	1	35·46	4·14	...
Chromium	54·0	7·76	1·40	3	52·00	8·68	...
Nickel	50·0	6·67	1·35	2	58·68	7·36	...
Arsenic	50·1	13·3	1·26	3	74·96	5·76	...
Selenium	62·5	18·5	1·175	4	79·20	6·67	...
Sulphur	48·2	15·5	1·025	4	32·06	12·13	$7·3 \times 10^{12}$

The values of frequencies calculated by the formula, agree well with those observed where such values are available and compare well with those obtained by Lindemann (*loc. cit.*), Wagstaff (*Phil. Mag.*, 1924, *vi*, 47, 87), Debye (Allen, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1917, **A**, 94, 100), and other formulae as indicated in Table III.

TABLE III.

Elements.	Einstein's formula.	Valencies as adopted by		Lindemann's formula based on photoelectric effect.	Debye formula.	Lindemann's m. p. formula.	Author's formula.	ν obs.
		Author.	Lindemann.*					
Mercury	1.46×10^{12}	2	1	2.0×10^{12}	...	1.3×10^{12}	2.1×10^{12}	2.2×10^{12}
Lead	2.2	2	2	2.5	1.49×10^{12}	1.84	1.64	1.9
Iodine	...	1	1	1.9	...	1.7	2.1	2.0
Copper	5.7	2	2	7.2	6.81	6.7	6.35	6.6
Aluminium	6.6	3	1	8.2	8.26	7.5	8.7	8.3
Zinc	3.73	2	4.36	5.8	4.8
Bromine	...	1	2.45	2.76	...
Silicon	...	4	9.6	9.96	...
Chlorine	...	1	3.68	4.14	...
Chromium	...	3	9.01	8.3	8.68	...
Sulphur	...	4	2	6.6	...	3.9	12.13	7.3
Nickel	6.6	2	8.2	7.36	...
Arsenic	...	3	4.36	5.76	...
Selenium	...	4	4.06	6.67	...

(Wagstaff, *loc. cit.*)

* These values of valencies have been adopted by Lindemann in his formula based on photoelectric effect (*Ber., Phys. Ges.*, 1911, 13, 1107).

SUMMARY.

A new formula has been proposed for the calculation of atomic frequencies from parachor, atomic volume, valency, Avogadro's number, atomic weight and the elementary charge, *viz.*,

$$\nu = \sqrt{k}. \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{P-V}{V} \cdot \frac{Ze^2}{r^3} \cdot \frac{N}{M}}$$

which bears out values observed experimentally as well as those calculated by other formulae.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE, CALCUTTA.

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